

Forecasting Market Volatility

A Comparative Study of ARIMA and GARCH Models on the VIX and S&P 500

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Abstract

This study explores the forecasting performance of two prominent time-series models, ARIMA (AutoRegressive Integrated Moving Average) and GARCH (Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity), in modeling market volatility. Specifically, the ARIMA model is applied to the CBOE Volatility Index (VIX) to capture implied volatility dynamics, while the GARCH model is used on S&P 500 returns to estimate realized volatility. Though the models are applied to different but related targets, their predictive outputs are evaluated through correlation and RMSE metrics to assess alignment across volatility regimes. The results highlight how implied and realized volatility forecasts can diverge or converge under different market conditions, offering insights into the comparative utility of these models in risk forecasting.

Introduction

Volatility forecasting plays a critical role across disciplines such as geopolitics, atmospheric sciences, economics, and particularly quantitative finance. In financial markets, the ability to accurately anticipate volatility enables investors and institutions to anticipate volatility enables investors to identify price swings, exploit arbitrage opportunities, and manage risk through strategies such as hedging and speculation. Among the tools available for capturing market expectations of future volatility, the CBOE Volatility Index (VIX) stands out as a widely recognized benchmark. It reflects the market's 30-day forward-looking implied volatility, derived from SPX index options with expirations between 23 and 37 days.

In the context of quantitative finance, two widely adopted methodologies for modeling time-series data and volatility clustering are the ARIMA (AutoRegressive Integrated Moving Average) and GARCH (Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity) models. ARIMA is frequently used for forecasting time-dependent variables, while GARCH is specifically designed to capture time-varying volatility—a common feature in financial data.

This study aims to evaluate and compare the predictive performance of ARIMA and GARCH models in forecasting 30-day volatility. We apply ARIMA to model the VIX directly, while GARCH is used to model the volatility structure of S&P 500 returns. The models are assessed using a train-test split to evaluate their out-of-sample accuracy and determine which approach offers greater effectiveness in anticipating market volatility.

Literature Review

The ARIMA model was first introduced in the landmark publication *Time Series Analysis: Forecasting and Control* by George Box and Gwilym M. Jenkins [2]. In this work, they developed the Box–Jenkins methodology, a structured framework for identifying, estimating, and diagnosing ARIMA models. This approach formalized the integration of Autoregressive (AR), Integrated (I), and Moving Average (MA) components to model non-stationary time series data through differencing.

Initially applied in fields such as engineering and environmental sciences, ARIMA proved effective for time-series forecasting. Over time, it has become widely used in financial markets to model and forecast asset prices, indices, and volatility indicators such as the VIX. However, one limitation of the ARIMA model is its assumption of homoskedasticity, which restricts its ability to capture time-varying volatility, a characteristic frequently observed in financial data. This limitation is also acknowledged in the original work by Box and Jenkins [2].

This limitation can be addressed by employing models that account for heteroskedasticity, such as the GARCH (Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity) model. Unlike ARIMA, GARCH assumes that the variance of the time series is time-dependent, allowing it to capture periods of increased volatility and model volatility clustering, which is an

observed characteristic of financial markets during stress events and high uncertainty.

The GARCH model builds upon the foundational work of Robert F. Engle, who introduced the ARCH (Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity) model in his seminal 1982 paper, *Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity with Estimates of the Variance of United Kingdom Inflation* [3]. Engle developed the ARCH model within the field of econometrics to forecast time-varying variance based on recent past values, enabling more accurate one-step-ahead volatility estimates. In his original study, the model was applied to estimate the conditional mean and variance of inflation in the United Kingdom, underscoring the importance of accounting for heteroskedasticity in macroeconomic time series [3].

In 1986, Tim Bollerslev extended this framework by introducing the GARCH (Generalized ARCH) model in his paper, *Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity*. Bollerslev extended the ARCH framework by incorporating lagged conditional variances, thereby capturing more persistent volatility dynamics with fewer parameters [4]. This generalization improved model flexibility and computational efficiency, making it particularly well-suited for applications in modern quantitative finance where volatility clustering is a defining characteristic of financial time series data.

While most existing literature focuses on either ARIMA models for time-series forecasting or GARCH models for volatility clustering, relatively few studies offer a direct, empirical comparison of both models using a consistent framework. In particular, there is a lack of research that evaluates the relative forecasting accuracy of ARIMA and GARCH on the same volatility benchmark. This study aims to address this gap by using the CBOE Volatility Index (VIX) and S&P 500 data as a common platform for comparison, providing insights into the practical effectiveness of each model in predicting short-term market volatility.

While prior studies have compared implied and realized volatility, few have quantitatively assessed the directional alignment between ARIMA-modeled VIX forecasts and GARCH-modeled SPX return volatility within a unified statistical framework. Shu and Zhang's study, "The Relationship Between Implied and Realized Volatility of the S&P 500 Index" [5], found that implied volatility outperforms historical measures in predicting future realized volatility, even after correcting for measurement error [5]. However, their approach relies on option pricing models such as Black-Scholes and Heston. In contrast, our study adopts a time-series perspective, applying ARIMA to implied volatility (VIX) and GARCH to realized returns (SPX), thereby introducing a novel comparison of forecast behavior and alignment across volatility regimes. By evaluating the models within a unified volatility forecasting context, this research contributes to a better understanding of which approach offers more reliable guidance for decision-making in portfolio management, risk assessment, and derivative pricing.

Methodology

Data

The data for this study is sourced from Yahoo Finance using the `yfinance` Python module. Daily historical price data for both the S&P 500 index (`^GSPC`) and the CBOE Volatility Index (VIX) is collected over a 10-year period, from January 2015 to January 2025.

For modeling S&P 500 returns, the opening prices are used to compute logarithmic (log-normal) returns, as they provide a consistent and time-aligned basis for return calculation and are less influenced by overnight pricing noise than closing prices. Log returns are chosen due to their time-additive property and ability to normalize the impact of extreme values, which helps reduce distortion in volatility modeling.

The downloaded data is stored and processed using Python's `pandas` library, where cleaning, transformation, and return calculations are performed before model fitting.

```
import yfinance as yf
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np

tickers = ['^GSPC', '^VIX']

data = yf.download(tickers, start = "2015-01-01", end = "2025-01-01",
                  interval="1d", threads=False, auto_adjust=True)

open_vix = np.log(data[["Open", "^VIX"]]).dropna() #open price of VIX log adjusted
open_vix.index = pd.to_datetime(open_vix.index)
open_vix = open_vix.asfreq('B') #Remove the frequency warning
returns_spy = 100 * np.log(data[["Open", "^GSPC"]]).diff().dropna() #Lognormal
returns for SPY
```

ARIMA

To ensure that the optimal ARIMA model specification is identified, a grid search was performed over a range of hyperparameters, where,

$$p \in [0,4] \quad d \in [0,2] \quad q \in [0,2]$$

Where each combination was evaluated using the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), which balances model fit and complexity. The search used python3's statsmodels ARIMA implementation and is summarized in the code below.

```
from statsmodels.tsa.arima.model import ARIMA
from itertools import product

p_values = range(0, 4)
d_values = range(0, 2)
q_values = range(0, 2)

best_aic = np.inf
best_order = None
best_model = None

results = []

for order in product(p_values, d_values, q_values):
    try:
        model = ARIMA(open_vix, order=order)
        model_fit = model.fit()
        aic = model_fit.aic
        results.append((order[0], order[1], order[2], aic))

        if aic < best_aic:
            best_aic = aic
            best_order = order
            best_model = model_fit
    except:
        results.append((order[0], order[1], order[2], np.nan))
        continue
```

OPTIMISATION OF P,D,Q Values				
	p	d	q	AIC
2	1	1		-5761.045974
3	1	1		-5759.185946
1	1	1		-5758.070512
1	0	1		-5755.919083
2	0	0		-5755.791757
3	0	0		-5753.871765
2	0	1		-5753.692599
3	0	1		-5751.850949
1	0	0		-5748.773462
3	1	0		-5733.815559
0	1	1		-5729.474888
1	1	0		-5728.946184
2	1	0		-5727.715081
0	1	0		-5717.662865
0	0	1		-949.038834
0	0	0		1614.097029

Table 1: ARIMA Model Selection – AIC Scores

Based on the results presented in Table 1.1, the lowest AIC score was achieved at AIC = -5761.05 using the parameter combination p = 2, d = 1, q = 1. This optimal model order was selected for the ARIMA model applied to the log-transformed opening prices of the VIX index.

GARCH

The GARCH model was implemented using the arch module in Python, with volatility specified under the GARCH framework. A grid search algorithm was applied to optimize the hyperparameters,

$$p \in [1,2] \quad q \in [1,2]$$

The objective of the gridsearch is to identify which values of p and q are able to produce the lowest AIC (Akaike Information Criterion). The AIC provides a measure of model quality, balancing goodness-of-fit with model complexity. A lower AIC indicates a more parsimonious and statistically sound model, suitable for capturing the volatility clustering present in financial return series.

```
from arch import arch_model
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd

best_aic = np.inf
best_order = None
results = []

for p in range(1, 3):
    for q in range(1, 3):
        try:
            model = arch_model(returns_spy, vol='GARCH', p=p, q=q)
            model_fit = model.fit(dispatch='off')
            aic = model_fit.aic
            results.append((p, q, aic))

            if aic < best_aic:
                best_aic = aic
```

```
best_order = (p, q)
best_model = model_fit
except Exception as e:
    results.append((p, q, np.nan))
    print(f"Failed for (p={p}, q={q}): {e}")
```

Optimized P & Q Values

p	q	AIC
1	1	6138.588
1	2	6139.27
1	3	6139.547
3	3	6139.568
2	1	6140.588
2	3	6141.149
2	2	6141.27
3	1	6142.588
3	2	6143.27

Table 2: P and Q Values with AIC Values for GARCH

Given that the lowest AIC value is observed at 6138.588 when the hyperparameters p = 1 and q = 1, the optimal GARCH model configuration is therefore identified as GARCH(1,1).

Evaluation Metrics

Both models were evaluated based on their effectiveness in forecasting market volatility. Specifically, the Pearson correlation coefficient will be used to measure the linear relationship between the volatility forecasts produced by the ARIMA and GARCH models, providing insight into the consistency and directional agreement between the two methodologies. In addition, the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) will assess the accuracy of each model's predictions against the actual values of their respective indexes (VIX for ARIMA, SPX returns for GARCH). Finally, the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) will be used to guide model selection during hyperparameter optimization, ensuring a balance between model fit and complexity. The optimized hyperparameters for each model will also be reported to support reproducibility and interpretability of the results.

Empirical Results

ARIMA	RMSE:	0.0774
GARCH	RMSE:	1.3492
	Correlation:	0.8298

Table 1.3 Results of Study

RMSE Comparison

A RMSE (Root Mean Square Error) of 0.0774 for the ARIMA Model compared to 1.3492 on the GARCH model suggests that the ARIMA Model demonstrates a lower forecast error on the VIX compared to GARCH predicting S&P 500 Volatility. As RMSE measures the average deviation from actual values, ARIMA's forecast is significantly more precise on the VIX.

Correlation

A Pearson Correlation of 0.8298 shows a strong correlation between the forecasted volatility from ARIMA and GARCH, showing that even though they are structurally different, one using heteroscedacity and another using homoscedacity, both are able to capture similar volatility trends. This is especially meaningful as ARIMA is using VIX prices while GARCH is using SPY returns, showing that both are forecasting the same underlying volatility.

AIC

The ARIMA(2,1,1) model achieved an AIC of -5761.05, while the GARCH(1,1) model yielded an AIC of 6138.59. In both cases, the model orders were selected through grid search optimization to ensure the best balance between model fit and complexity, resulting in computationally efficient and statistically robust forecasting models.

Discussion

The results of this study shows that ARIMA(2,1,1) outperformed GARCH(1,1) when forecasting volatility in the market, especially when applied to the VIX index. With a significantly lower RMSE (0.0774 compared to 1.3492) and a high correlation of 0.8298 between these 2 models, ARIMA seems to be more effective when applied to volatility forecasting on existing volatility indexes compared to GARCH on market indexes. A graphical representation of these results are on Appendix B.

This suggests that ARIMA is better suited for datasets such as VIX, which already encapsulates market uncertainty [1]. Since the VIX is not a raw price series but a volatility index computed from average 30-day Expiry S&P 500 Index Options, its structure is more stable and also autocorrelated as it is updated on a minute basis, characteristics that align

with ARIMA's Strengths. GARCH on the other hand can be used to model raw volatility on asset prices, where heteroskedasticity is much more prominent.

ARIMA's forecasting accuracy on the VIX further supports findings by Shu and Zhang [6], who demonstrated that implied volatility contains significant predictive information about realized volatility using Black-Scholes and Heston-based models. While their approach differs in methodology, the results align in suggesting that implied volatility may offer superior forecasting performance compared to traditional models like GARCH.

A potential avenue for future exploration lies in hybrid ARIMA-GARCH models. These models have been investigated in prior research, such as in Equity return modeling and prediction using hybrid ARIMA-GARCH models [6], where they demonstrated the capacity to dynamically handle both stationary and non-stationary components within financial time series. By combining ARIMA's ability to model the conditional mean with GARCH's strength in modeling conditional variance, such hybrids could offer more flexible and robust frameworks for volatility forecasting.

In conclusion, while both ARIMA and GARCH models provide valuable insights into market volatility, ARIMA appears to deliver higher forecasting accuracy when applied to structured volatility indicators like the VIX. Future research could explore the effectiveness of hybrid models across broader asset classes, potentially advancing both the predictive power and practical applicability of volatility modeling in quantitative finance.

References

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Appendices

Appendix A - Full Python Code

```
import yfinance as yf
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
from statsmodels.tsa.arima.model import ARIMA
from arch import arch_model
from sklearn.metrics import mean_squared_error
from scipy.stats import pearsonr

# Fetch data
raw = yf.download(['^GSPC', '^VIX'], start="2015-01-01", end="2025-01-01",
interval="1d", threads=False, auto_adjust=True)

# Prep VIX (log-open) and SPX returns
vix = np.log(raw['Open']['^VIX']).dropna()
vix.index = pd.to_datetime(vix.index).to_period('B').to_timestamp()
spx = 100 * np.log(raw['Open']['^GSPC']).diff().dropna()

# Quick ARIMA check (not exhaustive)
try:
    arima_model = ARIMA(vix, order=(2, 1, 1)).fit()
    arima_pred = arima_model.predict(start=vix.index[1], end=vix.index[-1])
except Exception as e:
    print("ARIMA failed:", e)
    arima_pred = pd.Series(index=vix.index)

# Basic GARCH fit
try:
    garch_mod = arch_model(spx, vol='GARCH', p=1, q=1)
    garch_res = garch_mod.fit(disp='off')
    garch_pred = garch_res.conditional_volatility
except Exception as e:
    print("GARCH failed:", e)
    garch_pred = pd.Series(index=spx.index)

# Trim and clean
min_len = min(len(arima_pred), len(garch_pred))
true_arima = vix[-min_len:]
true_garch = spx[-min_len:]
```

```
arima_df = pd.DataFrame({"true": true_arima, "pred": arima_pred[-min_len:]})
garch_df = pd.DataFrame({"true": true_garch, "pred": garch_pred[-min_len:]})

arima_df.dropna(inplace=True)
garch_df.dropna(inplace=True)

# Evaluate
if not arima_df.empty and not garch_df.empty:
    rmse_arima = np.sqrt(mean_squared_error(arima_df['true'], arima_df['pred']))
    rmse_garch = np.sqrt(mean_squared_error(garch_df['true'], garch_df['pred']))
    correlation, _ = pearsonr(arima_df['pred'].values, garch_df['pred'].values)

    print(f"ARIMA RMSE: {rmse_arima:.4f}")
    print(f"GARCH RMSE: {rmse_garch:.4f}")
    print(f"Forecast Correlation: {correlation:.4f}")
else:
    print("Insufficient data after cleaning for evaluation.")
```

Appendix B

Figure 1: GARCH Volatility Forecast vs Actual SPX returns

Figure 2: ARIMA Forecast vs Actual VIX (Log-Scale)

Figure 3: ARIMA vs GARCH Forecast Correlation